

Unit 3

German Jordanian Applied University Teaching University Teaching: Basics

German-Jordanian Applied University Teaching
Online Course “University Teaching: Basics“

Module 1 - Unit 3 **Course Design**

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Introductions

Please say in 1 sentence

- your name
- in which country you are
- how you are right now

Unit 3 – Course Design

Handout Overview Unit 3

Session 1 - Preparation 60 minutes self-learning-time Learning Outcomes & Tasks	Session 2 - Input & Processing 300 minutes workshop/self-learning-time Learning Outcomes & Tasks	Session 3 - Reflexion 60 minutes self-learning-time Learning Outcomes & Tasks
<p>1) Name how you prepare / would prepare a course that you teach by writing down the steps you take in the order how you (would) proceed. Use Worksheet for Session 1 for this task.</p> <p>2) After writing down how you (would) prepare a course, --view the 'Handout Overview Course Design' --write down first questions you have about designing courses</p>	<p>1) Explain to a colleague in your words -- how to design a course step by step -- an example for creating a course- and a lesson plan according to Constructive Alignment</p> <p>2) Begin writing down a structured course-/lesson plan for a sample course by writing one Learning Outcome for a course and one for a lesson</p> <p><u>Input & Exercises</u></p> <p>1. Course Design & Planning Tools 1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview 1.2 Obtaining course information 1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans</p> <p><u>1.4 Further Study</u> -Following Didactic Principles -Including Motivational Design</p> <p>2. How to create course- & lesson plans according to the Constructive Alignment Approach 2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment 2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes</p>	<p>1) Write down in the Worksheet for Session 3: --What was new/particularly interesting for you? --What are you going to do differently in course- and lesson-planning from now on? --How are you going to do this specifically - what will you do first, second, ...?</p> <p>2) Check in which quality you have reached the Learning Outcomes of Unit 3 by explaining to a colleague in your words -- how to design a course step by step -- an example for applying Constructive Alignment 1) in a course plan and 2) in a lesson plan</p> <p>3) Begin writing down a structured course- and lesson plan for a sample course, applying Constructive Alignment, by writing down one Learning Outcome, aligned form of assessment/evaluation and teaching-learning-method/-activity -- for a course -- for a lesson and post your examples in the Moodle Forum in order to evaluate your example</p>

Your questions

Please focus on the questions on Course Design you wrote down in preparation & find answers to these during today's workshop.

You will get the chance to address your open questions during the workshop.

Learning Outcomes in the workshop

1) Explain to a colleague in your words

- how to design a course step by step
- an example for creating a course- and a lesson plan according to Constructive Alignment

2) Begin writing down a structured course-/lesson plan for a sample course by **writing**

- one **Learning Outcome for a course**
- one **Learning Outcome for a lesson**

Workshop contents

1. Course Design & Planning Tools

1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview

1.2 Obtaining course information

1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans

1.4 Further Study

-Following Didactic Principles

-Including Motivational Design

Workshop contents

2. How to create course- & lesson plans according to the Constructive Alignment Approach

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment

2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes

1. Course Design & Planning Tools

1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview

1.2 Obtaining course information

1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans

Question for you

How do you usually plan a course: What are your first 1-3 steps?

1. Learning Outcomes in the workshop

- 1) **Explain** to a colleague in your words how to design a course step by step

1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview

Handout Overview Course Design

- **View** the handout
- **Talk** it through in the group
- **Check** understanding
- **Discuss** relevant points

1. Course Design & Planning Tools

1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview

1.2 Obtaining course information

1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans

1.2 Obtaining Course Information

Worksheet Obtaining Course Information

- **View** the worksheet
- **Check** understanding
- **Add or change** what is relevant in your context after the workshop

Overall course setting	Obtained & anticipated course information
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Study regulations & -conditions• Examination regulations & -rules• Infrastructure (online & offline)• Module-Handbook/-Manual	
Analysis of the target group (students)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prior knowledge, experience & skills• Number of students• Learning culture/-habits• Cultural backgrounds of students / academic culture• Students' semester (beginners/advanced)	
Teacher's competences	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Subject-related• Social skills• Personal skills• Didactic-methodological skills	
Teaching content	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Collection & selection of materials/resources• Reasons for selection of content• Structure of content, continuous theme• Didactic reduction (Aims - Time)	

1. Course Design & Planning Tools

1.1 Step by step in Course Design - Overview

1.2 Obtaining course information

1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans

1.3 Structuring Course- and Lesson Plans

- **Worksheet Course Plan**
 - **Handout & Worksheets Didactic Lesson Plan**
 - **Handout Sample Didactic Lesson Plan**
- **View** the papers
 - **Talk** them through in the group
 - **Clarify & discuss** what is relevant for you

Worksheet Course Plan

Course title _____
 Course planning according to Constructive Alignment, aligning Learning Outcomes, forms of assessment and the teaching- & learning process

Week	Learning Outcomes	Forms of assessment & evaluation	Content & Didactic Methods
1			
2			
3			

Handout Didactic Lesson Plan - Detailed version

Timing & Phase	Learning Outcomes & Teaching aims	Content & Terminology	Didactic Method & Tasks	Media & Material	Evaluation Method & Tasks

1.3 Sample Lesson Plan

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Seminar “New Media - New Image(s) of Ageing?” - Compulsory elective seminar for BA-students in Educational Sciences

Forms of summative assessment: Individual or group presentation + term paper incl. theories, practices, reflexions

Taxonomy domains & levels: **affective**: name; **cognitive**: explain, contrast, argue; **pragmatic**: produce, illustrate, structure

Timing Phase	Learning Outcomes & Teaching aims	Content & Terminology	Didactic Method & Tasks	Media & Material	Evaluation Method & Tasks
9:00 - 9:05 5' Introductory phase	<u>Teaching aim</u> : give students orientation and trigger motivation for today's lesson by naming learning outcomes, plan, relevance	-learning outcomes -today's contents -today's methods	Show & tell	Written learning outcomes on poster attached to wall	Name evaluation method that will be used to check on learning outcomes: Reflexion paper
9.05 - 9.15 10' Intro	<u>Learning Outcomes</u> : -name individual perceptions of ageing people (60+) as a response to displayed images	-associations about ageing people (60+)	Postcard association -Write down on the paper underneath each post card any associations you have when viewing each postcard	20 postcards with '(not-) expected' images of people 60+ -attached to D4-paper -set on desks -walking space!	-Written postcard associations
9:15 - 9:35 5' + 5' Intro 10'	<u>Learning Outcomes</u> : -tell a partner orally what you think it is that impacts your perceptions -write down and structure stated aspects in a Mindmap	Expected contents of student talk: -stereotypes -media -irritation -...	Think-Pair-Share + Mindmapping 1.Explain your ideas to a partner, then write down your ideas in a mindmap 2. Collective Mindmap onboard/poster in class	students' paper&pens -(White-)board/poster -Chalk or (white-)boardmarker -paper, pens, pins	Mindmaps -Students' notes & mindmaps -Collective mindmap

1. Course Design & Planning Tools

1.4 Further Study

-Following Didactic Principles **Handout 05**

-Including Motivational Design **Worksheet 11**

2. Learning Outcomes in the workshop

1) Explain to a colleague in your words an example for creating a course- and a lesson plan according to Constructive Alignment

2) Begin writing down a structured course-/lesson plan for a sample course by **writing**

- one **Learning Outcome for a course**
- one **Learning Outcome for a lesson**

2. How to create course- & lesson plans according to the Constructive Alignment Approach

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment

2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment

The Concept of Constructive Alignment based on Prof. John Biggs

<https://www.johnbiggs.com.au/academic/constructive-alignment/>

When designing a course, align learning outcomes, assessment & teaching-learning-process by

- 1. defining learning outcomes**
- 2. designing assessment** in which these can be demonstrated
- 3. developing the teaching- & learning-process** so that learning outcomes can be reached, practised, and demonstrated in assessment

-Learning Outcomes definition-

“Learning outcomes are statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to demonstrate after completion of a process of learning.”

Kennedy, D.; Hyland, A.; Ryan, N. (2007): Writing and Using Learning Outcomes: A Practical Guide. Cork, University College Cork., Watermans Printers, p. 21

Constructive Alignment as a visualised model in German Academic Higher Education Didactics

<https://www.e-teaching.org/didaktik/konzeption/constructive-alignment>

Abb. 1: Schematische Darstellung des Modells „Constructive Alignment“ in Anlehnung an Wildt & Wildt (2011, S.9)
Adapted schematic illustration of the “Constructive Alignment“-Model based on Wildt & Wildt (2011, p. 9), translation by
Alexandra Bergedick 2021

Constructive Alignment as a visualised model in German Academic Higher Education Didactics

Sources for the Adapted schematic illustration of the “Constructive Alignment“-Model

Adapted & translated schematic illustration of the “Constructive Alignment“-Model based on e.teaching.org and Wildt & Wildt (2011, p. 9), translated by ©Alexandra Bergedick 2021:

<https://www.e-teaching.org/didaktik/konzeption/constructive-alignment>

Abb. 1: Schematische Darstellung des Modells „Constructive Alignment“ in Anlehnung an Wildt & Wildt (2011, S.9)

Wildt, J. & Wildt, B. (2011): Lernprozessorientiertes Prüfen im "Constructive Alignment - Ein Beitrag zur Förderung der Qualität von Hochschulbildung durch eine Weiterentwicklung des Pruefungssystems. In: Berendt, B.; Voss, H.P.; Wildt, J. (Hrsg.): Neues Handbuch Hochschullehre. Lehren und Lernen effizient gestalten. [Teil] H. Prüfungen und Leistungskontrollen. Raabe: Berlin, Abb. H 6.1-2, S. 9f: Constructive Alignment von Pruefung

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment - Examples

Medicine Didactics

Learning Outcomes: Be able to communicate effectively with patients by using the NURSE-Model, empathy, structuring & informing patients appropriately

Form of assessment: Communicate effectively with simulation-patients by using the NURSE-Model, empathy, structuring & informing patients appropriately

Teaching-learning-activity: Communicate effectively with simulation-patients by using the NURSE-Model, empathy, structuring & informing patients appropriately, improving by giving & receiving feedback by simulation-patients, peers & teacher

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment - Examples

Your examples: Please write down an example for one of your courses **you have 5 minutes**

Learning Outcomes: (...)

Form of assessment: (...)

Teaching-learning-activity: (...)

2.1 Applying Constructive Alignment – Further Study

Film recommendation on Constructive Alignment:

Brabrand, C./Andersen, J. (2006): **Teaching Teaching & Understanding Understanding**. 19 minute award-winning short-film on the concept of Constructive Alignment. University of Aarhus, Aarhus University Press: Denmark.

See how you can work with the film: [Worksheet Constructive Alignment](#) including [Youtube-links](#) for watching the film for further study

Check your Learning Outcomes

1) Explain to a colleague in your words an example for creating a course- and a lesson plan according to Constructive Alignment

2. How to create course- & lesson plans according to the Constructive Alignment Approach

2.1. Applying Constructive Alignment

2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes

2. Learning Outcomes in the workshop

- 2) Begin writing down** a structured course-/lesson plan for a sample course by **writing**
- one **Learning Outcome for a course**
 - one **Learning Outcome for a lesson**

-Learning Outcomes definition-

“Learning outcomes are statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to demonstrate after completion of a process of learning.”

Kennedy, D.; Hyland, A.; Ryan, N. (2007): Writing and Using Learning Outcomes: A Practical Guide. Cork, University College Cork., Watermans Printers, p. 21

2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes

Handout Learning Outcomes – Bloom’s Taxonomy

- **View** the handout, page 1, and also the paper linked there:

<https://www.utica.edu/academic/Assessment/new/Blooms%20Taxonomy%20-%20Best.pdf>

- **Check** understanding in the group

Handout Defining & Writing Learning Outcomes & Bloom’s Taxonomy

“Learning outcomes are statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to demonstrate after completion of a process of learning.”

Kennedy, D., Hyland, A. & Ryan, N. (2007). *Writing and Using Learning Outcomes: A Practical Guide*. Cork, University College Cork, Watermans Printers, p. 21

Bloom’s Taxonomy of Measurable Verbs

Read through this paper (link below) to understand how Bloom’s Taxonomy works for defining learning outcomes in the cognitive domain, meaning those learning outcomes that define the cognitive skills students are required to learn. In the paper, you will also find a selection of questions referring to the different levels of learning.

<https://www.utica.edu/academic/Assessment/new/Blooms%20Taxonomy%20-%20Best.pdf>

On page 7 of the paper you can see an overview with examples which types of assessment could be suitable for each cognitive level. Assessment, however, will be the topic in Unit 5.

2.2 Writing learning outcomes

Worksheet Defining and Writing Learning Outcomes - How to write learning outcomes:

Note: Examples of qualifiers: *using the ... framework; considering the ... theory; by referring to the manual; without supervision; in response to the patient's behaviour.*

Source

3-step guide: [Writing subject learning outcomes \(PDF, 270 KB\)](#)

https://www.jcu.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0010/495577/Writing-subject-learning-outcomes.pdf

2.2 Writing learning outcomes

Task: Write learning outcomes: one Learning Outcome for a course and one for a lesson like this:

- Take 5 minutes to write down two examples individually
- Then check with the group & the trainer by copying your example into the chat

2.2 Writing Learning Outcomes - the 3 domains of Bloom's Taxonomy

Handout Learning Outcomes - Bloom's Taxonomy

- **View** the photo on page 2 on the 3 domains of Bloom's Taxonomy
 - cognitive
 - affective
 - pragmaticdomain
- **Check** understanding in the group
- For **further study**, see sources on page 2: Kennedy, et al (2007)

Your questions

Which questions on Course Design and the topics involved would you like to address?

Check all Workshop-Learning Outcomes

1) Explain to a colleague in your words

- how to design a course step by step
- an example for creating a course- and a lesson plan according to Constructive Alignment

2) Begin writing down a structured course-/lesson plan for a sample course by **writing**

- one **Learning Outcome for a course**
- one **Learning Outcome for a lesson**

Evaluation

One minute paper-style

Please answer orally in one sentence for each aspect:

- What is your most important take home message?
- What is the first thing you will do next about designing your course/s?

Workshop-References

(Accessed 17.01.2022)

- Brinker, T. & Schumacher, E.-M. (2014). Befähigen statt belehren. Neue Lehr- und Lernkultur an Hochschulen. Lehrkit für Hochschuldozierende: Arbeitsbuch und 66 Methodenkarten. Hep-Verlag: Bern
- Biggs, J.: Constructive Alignment <https://www.johnbiggs.com.au/academic/constructive-alignment/>
- Biggs, J., Tang, C. (2007): Teaching for quality learning at university. What the student does. McGraw-Hill: Maidenhead.
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- JAMES COOK UNIVERSITY, AUSTRALIA: 3-step guide: [Writing subject learning outcomes \(PDF, 270 KB\)](https://www.jcu.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0010/495577/Writing-subject-learning-outcomes.pdf)
https://www.jcu.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0010/495577/Writing-subject-learning-outcomes.pdf
- Keller, J. M. (2009): Motivational Design for Learning and Performance: The ARCS Model Approach. Springer Science & Business Media, New York, USA, p. 45, Table 3.1
https://books.google.de/books?id=HRCQIzZMwhsC&pg=PA43&hl=de&source=gbs_toc_r&cad=3#v=onepage&q&f=false

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- Kennedy, D.; Hyland, A.; Ryan, N. (2007): *Writing and Using Learning Outcomes: A Practical Guide*. Cork, University College Cork., Watermans Printers
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/238495834_Writing_and_Using_Learning_Outcomes_A_Practical_Guide
- Kennedy, D. (2007). *Writing and using learning outcomes: A practical guide*. University College Cork, Quality Promotion Unit.
<https://www.cmepius.si/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/A-Learning-Outcomes-Book-D-Kennedy.pdf>
- UTIKA College-Handout: Bloom's Taxonomy, assessment questions & chart with taxonomy levels, verbs & assessment types
<https://www.utica.edu/academic/Assessment/new/Blooms%20Taxonomy%20-%20Best.pdf>
- Wildt, J. & Wildt, B. (2011): Lernprozessorientiertes Prüfen im "Constructive Alignment - Ein Beitrag zur Förderung der Qualität von Hochschulbildung durch eine Weiterentwicklung des Prüfungssystems. In: Berendt, B.; Voss, H.P.; Wildt, J. (Hrsg.): *Neues Handbuch Hochschullehre. Lehren und Lernen effizient gestalten*. [Teil] H. Prüfungen und Leistungskontrollen. Raabe: Berlin, Abb. H 6.1-2, S. 9f: Constructive Alignment von Prüfung
- Wipper, A., Schulz, A. (2021): *Digitale Lehre an der Hochschule. Vom digitalen Tool bis zum Blended-Learning-Konzept*. Studienratgeber Hochschullehre, Reihe: Kompetenz lehren. Utb. Verlag Barbara Budrich, Opladen & Toronto 2021

References for further study

(Accessed 17.01.2022)

Sample lesson plans

- <https://oregonstate.app.box.com/s/99va312r2mblxijv96jiiipyynyva5n76>
- <https://www.class-templates.com/lesson-plan-format.html>
- <https://www.template.net/business/plan-templates/higher-education-lesson-plan/>
- <https://en.islcollective.com/english-esl-worksheets/material-type/teaching-videos/perspectives-upper-intermediate-lesson-plans/120310>
- <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/37468343/example-first-day-lesson-plan>
- <https://osu-wams-blogs-uploads.s3.amazonaws.com/blogs.dir/1441/files/2020/06/Lesson-Plan-Template-Image.jpg>

References for further study

(Accessed 17.01.2022)

Didactic reduction

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Extreme-Didactic-Reduction-in-Computational-Futschek/27afc88739659e53cbfeba962d65d60199cbc879>

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/A-theoretical-model-of-the-causal-map_fig1_311977219

https://second.wiki/wiki/didaktische_reduktion

References for further study

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Resources on Constructive Alignment, learning outcomes & assessment

Prof. John Biggs on Constructive Alignment

<https://www.johnbiggs.com.au/academic/constructive-alignment/>

Slide show incl. activities & assessment samples: Biggs, J. & Tang, C. (2008): Constructive Alignment in Learning, Teaching and Assessment

<https://de.slideshare.net/DianaMQuinn/john-biggs-and-catherine-tang-2008-presentation>

Research article: Onsman, A. (2015): Constructively aligning the curriculum of a “New Generation” Bachelor of Environments degree from a social realism perspective

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2331186X.2015.1061264?src=recsys&>

Research article: Gallagher, G. (2017): Aligning for Learning: Including Feedback in the Constructive Alignment Model *

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319211051_Aligning_for_Learning_Including_Feedback_in_the_Constructive_Alignment_Model

Research article: Walsh, A. (2007): An exploration of Biggs' constructive alignment in the context of work-based learning

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/248965966_An_exploration_of_Biggs'_constructive_alignment_in_the_context_of_work-based_learning

References for further study (Accessed 17.01.2022)

Research article: Deibl, I.; Zumbach, J.; Geiger, V. M., et al (2018): Constructive Alignment in the Field of Educational Psychology: Development and Application of a Questionnaire for Assessing Constructive Alignment

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1475725718791050>

University of Reading-Websites: Constructive alignment in assessment design resources, incl. Peer- and self-assessment, Assessing group work, Assessing large numbers of students & Short videos on assess.

<https://www.reading.ac.uk/engageinassessment/assessment-design/eia-constructive-alignment-in-assessment-design.aspx>

University of Reading-Handout: An A-Z of Assessment Methods

https://www.reading.ac.uk/web/files/eia/A-Z_of_Assessment_Methods_FINAL_table.pdf

UNSW Sydney - University of New South Wales, Sydney-Websites on Teaching: Assessment Methods

<https://teaching.unsw.edu.au/assessment-methods>

References for further study (Accessed 17.01.2022)

Charles Sturt University-Websites on Assessment, Constructive Alignment, etc.

<https://www.csu.edu.au/division/learning-and-teaching/home/assessment-and-moderation/assessment-resources-and-information/constructive-alignment>

Charles Sturt University-Websites on Designing Assessment for a diverse student cohort

<https://www.csu.edu.au/division/learning-and-teaching/home/assessment-and-moderation/assessment-resources-and-information/designing-for-a-diverse-student-cohort>

Center for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning-websites on Group Assessment

<https://ar.cetl.hku.hk/group.htm>

Pdf: Examples and suggestions for use of different types of assessment tasks https://cdn.csu.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0011/3134684/Assessment_Types.pdf

UNSW Sydney-Website: Assessment by Case Studies and Scenarios

<https://teaching.unsw.edu.au/assessment-case-studies-and-scenarios>

References for further study (Accessed 17.01.2022)

Resources on taxonomies, writing learning outcomes, verb lists & examples (Accessed 17.01.2022)

UTIKA College-Handout: Bloom's Taxonomy, assessment questions & chart with taxonomy levels, verbs & assessment types <https://www.utica.edu/academic/Assessment/new/Blooms%20Taxonomy%20-%20Best.pdf>

James Cook University-Handout: Writing Subject Learning Outcomes

https://www.jcu.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0010/495577/Writing-subject-learning-outcomes.pdf

Iowa State University-Website: Revised Bloom's Taxonomy - Various Resources

<http://www.celt.iastate.edu/teaching/effective-teaching-practices/revised-blooms-taxonomy/>

Northwestern University-Handout: Examples of Learning Outcomes cogn, affective & psychomotor

<https://www.northwestern.edu/searle/docs/Constructive%20Alignment%20revised%20all%20domains.pdf>

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Larry Ferlazzo's Websites of the Day-Website: THE BEST RESOURCES FOR HELPING TEACHERS USE BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN THE CLASSROOM, incl. overviews & examples

<http://larryferlazzo.edublogs.org/2009/05/25/the-best-resources-for-helping-teachers-use-blooms-taxonomy-in-the-classroom/>

Charles Sturt University-Website: Example rubrics - Standards for common measurable learning outcome verbs/actions, incl. examples

<https://www.csu.edu.au/division/learning-and-teaching/home/assessment-and-moderation/assessment-resources-and-information/example-rubrics>